

ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE, TRANSFORMATIONAL AND ETHICAL LEADERSHIP: A STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL ON ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT OF TEACHERS

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Organizational Climate, Transformational and Ethical Leadership: A Structural Equation Model on Organizational Commitment of Teachers

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Abstract

This study determined the best-fit model on teachers' organizational commitment as influenced by organizational climate, transformational and ethical leadership of school heads among public elementary schools in Region XI, Philippines. It was conducted from August to December 2022. The study used quantitative, non-experimental correlational research using Structural Equation Model (SEM). The 400 teachers among public elementary schools were determined using the stratified sampling procedure. Mean, Pearson r , and SEM were used as statistical tools. Moreover, adapted survey questionnaires were used to contextualize to the local setting. The result showed that the level of organizational climate of schools was high while the transformational and ethical leadership of school heads were very high. The organizational commitment of teachers was also very high. Further, the exogenous variables: organizational climate, transformational and ethical leadership were correlated with the endogenous variable: organizational commitment of teachers. Model 3 came out as the best-fit structural model for teachers' organizational commitment as it indicated that by structural modifications, the organizational climate was described by trusting relationship as well as job and goal setting freedom. Transformational leadership was described by transactional and execution, while ethical leadership was measured by people orientation and integrity. On the other hand, organizational commitment was defined by affective commitment and continuance commitment. This implies that schools may focus on implementing leadership training enhancement activities for all school heads in public elementary schools as part of their staff development program.

Keywords: *organizational climate, transformational leadership, ethical leadership, organizational commitment, Structure Equation Model*

Introduction

In the modern context of the educational profession, teaching has been perceived as a complex and demanding profession and the question on how to build up commitment among teachers is still a problem (Celep, 2010; Chavez, 2012; Day, 2014; Elliot & Crosswell, 2011). Research reported that teachers with low organizational commitment often come late to work and tend to be frequently absent from work by abusing sick leave which caused loss of valuable instruction time due to ineffective substitute teachers or class cancellation. Besides, teachers with low organizational commitment tend to migrate to another school or resign from the teaching profession. Subsequently, teachers who show low organizational commitment are only interested with their own success rather than the organization's success which affects their involvement to provide quality education and their ability to help students towards academic achievement. (Gaziel, 2014; Fresko, Kfir & Nasser, 2007; Labatmediene, Kaunas, Endriulaitiene & Gustainiene, 2017; Selamat, Nordin & Adnan, 2013; Shapira-Lishchinsky & Rosenblatt, 2010).

In relation, the organizational commitment of teachers is very important since it is essential for school effectiveness and indirectly affects the learning outcome of the students. Therefore, schools more than ever need strong and committed teachers to attain educational goals. In the educational system, committed teachers have more capabilities to cope with the obstacles in teaching at the classroom setting. An effective teacher is a committed one who is constantly updating his/her knowledge to serve the students. Thus, teachers' organizational commitment is a variable that affects the quality of teaching. Also, the commitment of teachers plays a crucial role in the establishment of a cohesive effort inside the school organization. Therefore, every school organization needs to build up basic efforts to encourage and empower the teachers to heighten their commitment towards their school organization. With this, it will enable the school organization to meet future challenges and simultaneously preserve the attachment of teachers to the school organization (Ahmad, Yunus, Norwani & Musa, 2012; Bernaldez & Gempes, 2016; Haftkhavani, Faghiharam & Araghieh, 2012; Hamid, Nordin, Adnan & Sirun, 2013; Saki, 2009).

Considering the importance of organizational commitment of teachers, the researcher reviewed the various factors which may affect organizational commitment. These may include organizational climate, transformational leadership, and ethical leadership. Studies revealed that organizational climate and organizational commitment are significantly related. Dimensions of organizational climate had greater influence on organizational commitment. It was identified that positive climate can contribute to strong employee commitment. Specifically, organizational climate variables such as motivation, decision making, communication, leadership, and goal setting are significant predictors of organizational commitment (Abdullah & Hasan, 2016; Bahrami, Taheri, Montazer Alalfaraj, & Dehghani Tafti, 2013; Iqbal, 2008; Laschinger, Finegan & Shamian, 2011; Lok, Westwood & Crawford, 2015; McMurray, Scott & Pace, 2014; Warsi, Fatima & Sahibzada, 2009).

Further, teacher commitment is predominantly derived from continuance and affective organizational commitment, shaped by identity orientation influenced by social and collective identity, as highlighted by Guhao (2019). Guhao emphasizes the importance of teachers

displaying verbal and nonverbal immediacy behaviors to reinforce this commitment. In summary, Guhao (2019) emphasizes the interplay between organizational commitment, identity orientation, and the communicative conduct of teachers.

Similarly, leadership styles such as transformational and ethical leadership can also influence organizational commitment. There is considerable research now available suggesting that transformational leadership is positively associated with organizational commitment in a variety of organizational settings and cultures. Transformational leaders can influence followers' organizational commitment by promoting higher levels of intrinsic value associated with goal accomplishment, emphasizing the linkages between follower effort and goal achievement, and by creating a higher level of personal commitment on the part of the leader and followers to a common vision, mission, and organizational goals. Moreover, transformational leaders influence followers' organizational commitment by encouraging followers to think critically by using novel approaches, involving followers in decision-making processes, inspiring loyalty, while recognizing and appreciating the different needs of each follower to develop his or her personal potential (Avolio, Zhu, Koh & Bathia, 2014; Bass & Avolio, 2014; Bono & Judge, 2013; Walumbwa & Lawler, 2013; Yammarino, Spangler, & Bass, 2013).

In parallel, ethical leadership is also associated with employee organizational commitment. Leaders are the key to determine the outcome of organizational goals and to set the tone for employee commitment which may include promotion, appraisal, and strategies. If leaders are perceived to be ruthless and inconsiderate at work with others, employees tend to be less committed at work. Employees want to be associated with ethical leaders who are honest, credible, respectful, and fair. Organizations can achieve better employee commitment when employees can work for truly responsible and ethical leaders. Thus, failing to be an ethical leader can lead to decrease employee commitment and consequently lead to poor level of employee productivity (Agha, Nwekpa & Eze, 2017; Brown & Mitchell, 2010; Collins, 2011; Crane & Matten, 2014; Fisher & Lovell, 2013; Upadhyay & Singh, 2010).

In addition, various literature and related studies are herein presented that lead to the understanding of the variables under consideration re organizational climate, transformational leadership, ethical leadership and organizational commitment.

On organizational climate, it presented that organizational climate cannot be seen or touched but it is real, and it is like air in the room, and it surrounds and affects everything within the organization. Organizational climate is the air that organizational culture generates. It was indicated that organizational culture is the ways of effecting organizational members. Organizational climate is the shared values, beliefs, norms, and understanding of the group members. Further, organizational climate is a psychological environment, and it shows in what degree it is meaningful for the group employees (Bridge, 2013; Ensari & Zembat, 2009; Terzi, 2010; Schein, 2007; Varol, 2013).

In the same manner, schools are the prime element in our education system. For personnel working in a school, adapting to the schools' purpose, accepting the values, beliefs, and norms, and behaving appropriately are within scope of organizational climate. There are many factors that affect organizational climate. But the prime factor in organizational climate are people and interaction between groups. Interaction of school with its environment, the balance between the purpose of the school and individual's purpose, the degree of the success of the realization of school's purpose, manager at school and other professional people's personal traits are the primary effects on the organizational climate (Aydin, 2013; Bursahoglu, 2013; Ceyda & Sevinc, 2012; Topcu, 2008).

Moreover, one of the key conditions to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of the healthy climate school is organization climate. School research point out that effective schools have positive organizational climate. If there is no positive organization climate, it is not possible to improve the school. Also, if there is open communications and sincere relations at school, then we can say that there is positive organizational climate at school. Positive climate is an important concept that will facilitate the success and welfare level we desire to see in schools. There are important responsibilities for school members in building an environment where they want to be a part of, and where mutual sincerity, trust and respect exist (Ceyda & Sevinc, 2012; Ozden, 2014; Taymaz, 2013).

The first indicator of organizational climate is trusting relationship. This factor explained organizational climate in terms of widespread trust experienced by members of the organization. The subordinates are perceived to be respectfully treated, their competencies are considered as a contributing factor to relate professionally with each other and develop a trusting relationship within the group. Subordinates perceived their superiors as trustworthy and approachable for discussing and solving a variety of work-related problem (Shanker, 2015).

The second indicator is job and goal setting freedom. This factor explained the organizational climate in terms of perception of people related to performance goals and opportunities for independent thoughts and action that can help them and the organization alike. It is also perceived by the subordinate that it gives full freedom to decide about completing their assigned job (Shanker, 2015).

Similarly, the significance of job performance is evident in the study, which employed Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) to investigate its influence on organizational commitment among 400 public school teachers in Region XI, Philippines (Guhao & Cabayag, 2024). The findings identified significant correlations of self-efficacy, job performance, transformational and organizational commitment.

The third and last indicator is organizational power direction. This factor signifies direction of power in channelizing organizational energies. Similarly, due to great show of power or power possessiveness it tends to assign more power to its upper echelon and sets

higher standards of performance to lead other organizations in the same field as that of organization itself (Shanker, 2015).

On transformational leadership, it is presented that transformational leaders as those who mobilize their efforts to reform organizations, in part by raising followers' consciousness beyond personal interests to be more in line with organizational goals and vision. Interactive and highly participatory encounters among all members of a team are key ingredients. Through these interactions, visions emerge, consensus is built, plans are discussed, and potential roadblocks are explored, increasing buy-in and accountability among team members. Leaders influence the process by promoting intellectual stimulation, inspiring motivation and taking each member's needs into consideration (Bass, 2015; Burns, 2018).

In addition, the impact that transformational leadership has on members of an organization can best be examined by comparing it to transactional leadership, where leaders approach followers with an eye to exchanging one thing for another. A transformational leader mobilizes his followers toward reform by an appeal to values and emotions. Transformational leadership focuses more on self-actualization - a desire for the betterment of the team or organization. Thus, transformational approaches to leadership have a wide range of potential benefits. At the organization level, transformational leadership practices can produce strategic organizational change. Perceived transformational actions have also been shown to increase staff satisfaction and reduce stress and burnout (Edwards, Knight, Broome & Flynn, 2010; Martin & Epitropaki, 2011; Judge & Piccolo, 2014; Seltzer, Numerof, & Bass, 2009; Waldman, Javidan & Varella, 2014).

Furthermore, the following are the indicators of transformational leadership. The first indicator is charisma in which a leader is a role model who shows true dedication, trust, and respect to others, who in turn, do the same to others. The second indicator is social in which a leader helps others to learn by coaching and mentoring them. He creates challenging environments to help them reach their full potential. When others have difficulties, he is not afraid to empathize with them and helps guide them. The third indicator is vision in which the leader provides challenging visions and helps people to understand them so that they are motivated to join in. The fifth indicator is transactional in which the leader ensures others understand what he expects from them by using mutual agreement. In addition, he ensures that if poor performance does occur, he takes action to ensure it does not affect the moral of the team. The sixth indicator is delegation which refers to how a leader delegates both the task and that he/she has the authority to get things accomplished. The last indicator is execution in which a leader does delegate as many tasks as possible with the authority to accomplish them, as a good steward of the department's resources, and does follow-up to ensure things are going as planned and we are not wasting time (Clark, 2011).

On ethical leadership, it is presented that the role of school leaders is very important to focus specifically on strategies to increase the level of teachers' commitment to ensure the quality and educational outcomes of school is always at a high level (Anderman, Belzer & Smith, 2011; Ismail & Daud, 2014).

Furthermore, ethical leadership is a means to improve their selves as followers will see and evaluate what is seen in a leader. Studies found teachers trust to principals most influenced by practices such as effective leadership, consistency, reliability, openness, respect and integrity. These practices are likely to encourage teachers to be more committed to their careers (Handford & Leithwood, 2013; Ismail & Daud, 2014).

Likewise, starting early 1990, the reform leadership and insistence on the need for ethical leadership became more apparent when the researchers began to pay more attention to the needs of these, particularly in the public and private sector organizations This is because ethical leader behavior identified can be a role model for their followers to follow and emulate (White & Lean, 2018; Yukl, Mahsud, Hassan & Prussia, 2011).

In addition, ethical leadership is the demonstration of normatively appropriate conduct through personal actions and interpersonal relationships and the promotion of such conduct to followers through two-way communication, reinforcement and decision-making. Ethical leadership is composed of two main aspects of individual moral and moral manager. Individual moral aspect refers to the personality characteristics of the leader as seen, the behavior and decision-making process. The moral aspect of the manager refers to deliberate efforts by a leader to influence others (role models), guiding the ethical behavior of followers such as communicating about ethical standards and discipline employees who demonstrate unethical behavior. Thus, the combination of the individual aspects of moral and moral managers to have an ethical leadership style is seen in contrast to the style of leadership of others. This is because ethical leaders, although they become role models who exhibit personality and appropriate behavior, also use aspects of reward and punishment to stimulate ethical conduct among followers (Brown, Treviño & Harrison, 2015; Ismail & Daud, 2014; Trevino, Brown & Hartman, 2013).

Additionally, there are seven indicators of ethical leadership. The first indicator is people orientation or having a true concern for people. The people orientation component in ethical leadership reflects genuinely caring about, respecting, and supporting subordinates and where even possible ensuring that their needs are met (Kalshoven, Den Hartog & De Hoogh, 2011; Kanungo & Conger, 2013; Treviño et al., 2013).

The second indicator is fairness which is seen as an important form of ethical leader behavior. Ethical leaders act with integrity and treat others fairly. They make principle and fair choices, are trustworthy and honest, do not practice favoritism, and take responsibility for their own actions (Brown et al., 2015; De Hoogh & Den Hartog, 2018; Kalshoven et al., 2011; Treviño et al., 2013).

The third indicator is power sharing. Ethical leaders allow subordinates a say in decision making and listen to their ideas and concerns and also provide followers with voice. Sharing power also allows subordinates more control and makes them less dependent on their leaders (Brown et al, 2015; De Hoogh & Den Hartog, 2009; Yukl, 2016).

The fourth indicator is concern for sustainability. This refers to ethical leaders' concern for sustainability of stakeholders and society. In line with this, ethical leaders take the effects of their behavior on the surroundings into account, including the society and environment. It takes a responsibility point of view and argues that sustainable leaders act beyond their self-interests (Ferdig, 2017; Kalshoven et al., 2011; Kanungo & Mendonca, 2018).

The fifth indicator is ethical guidance which means ethical leader conveys standards regarding ethical conduct. Organizations and top management set rules, standards, and codes of conduct, which provide guidelines for ethical behavior and leaders, raise subordinates' awareness of such guidelines and use rewards and punishments to hold subordinates responsible for their actions (Kalshoven et al., 2011; Treviño et al., 2013).

The sixth indicator is role clarification. Ethical leaders are transparent and engage in open communication which is known as role clarification. Ethical leaders clarify responsibilities, expectations and performance goals, so that subordinates know what is expected from them and understand when their performance is up to par. Subordinates do not worry unnecessarily about unclear expectations and know how they can meaningfully contribute to meeting the unit's or organization's goals (Brown et al., 2015; Kalshoven et al., 2011).

The last indicator is integrity which is based on the behavioral integrity literature. Integrity behaviors are described as word-deed alignment or the extent to which what one says is in line with what one does (Ferdig, 2017; Kalshoven et al., 2011). Leaders who keep promises and behave consistently can be trusted or believed because they work or behave as expected. Similarly, leaders are being ethical when they keep promises and behave consistently. Thus, ethical leaders keep their promises and act consistently, in a predictable way, which we label integrity (Kalshoven, 2010; Yukl, 2016).

On the organizational commitment, it is presented that the school organizational commitment of teachers is very important for achieving school effectiveness which in turn influences students' learning outcomes. Additionally, teachers' organizational commitment plays an essential role in establishing a unified effort within a school organization. Thus, it is necessary for every individual in the school organization to build up efforts to strengthen teachers' commitment towards the school organization. Herewith, this will allow the school organization to come across impending organizational challenges and concurrently maintain the organizational commitment of teachers (Ahmad, Yunus, Norwani & Musa, 2012; Hamid, Nordin, Adnan & Sirun, 2013; Bernaldez, 2016).

In conjunction, to achieve success in organizational commitment, every organization needs effective leadership. Studies found out that teachers trust school leaders if they possess effective leadership, consistency, reliability, openness, respect and integrity which constitutes ethical leadership. These practices are likely to encourage teachers to be more committed to their careers (Handford & Leithwood, 2013; Ismail & Daud, 2014).

In parallel, the commitment of the people inside the organization directly impacts their job performance (Malhotra & Mukherjee, 2014; Steyrer, Schiffinger & Lang, 2014). To nurture a high level of commitment of the organizational members, every leader should reassure participative decision-making, treat organizational members with respect, and show fairness and caring attitude towards them. As organizational leaders display ethical leadership, there will be an increased organizational commitment among employees (Cullen, Parboteeah & Victor, 2013; Ferreira, 2012; Walumbwa & Lawler, 2013).

Furthermore, organizational commitment is defined as the degree to which workers identify with a certain organization and its objectives and desires to sustain organizational attachment. Additionally, it was argued that commitments comprise 'behavioral terms' that refer to what actions a commitment entail. These terms can take the type of local and discretionary behavior. A focal behavior is one accepted to be indispensable to the idea of commitment to a specific target, such that each of the three outlooks ought to anticipate this behavior. It is the behavior to which a person is bound by his or her dedication. For instance, for organizational commitment, the focal behavior is speculated to be keeping up organizational attachment. Conversely, discretionary behaviors are 'optional', as in the organizational members have some adaptability in characterizing the behavioral terms of their commitment (Lekhetso, 2013; Meyer & Herscovitch, 2011; Saravanan & Udhayashankar, 2015).

Relatively, a three-component model of commitment was established by Meyer and Allen who perhaps governs research regarding organizational commitment (Jaros, 2007; Meyer, Stanley, Herscovitch & Topolnytsky, 2012; Meyer & Herscovitch, 2011). This model suggests three domains of organizational commitment are experienced by the organizational members, namely, affective, normative, and continuance. In particular, the first indicator which is affective commitment is the emotional attachment of the people to the organization and a conviction in its values. This domain reveals commitment based on emotional connections the workers cultivate with the organization principally through helpful job experiences (Meyer et al., 2012; Saravanan & Udhayashankar, 2012).

Further, the second indicator which is continuance commitment refers to the observed cost-effective value of staying with the organization compared to separating from it. This domain reveals commitment based on both social and economic cost of exiting the organization (Meyer et al., 2012; Saravanan & Udhayashankar, 2012).

Moreover, the third indicator which is normative commitment refers to the responsibility to stay with the organization for ethical causes. Further, this commitment domain is based on professed duty towards the organization such as rooted in the reciprocity standards. This commitment model has been utilized by most researchers to predict imperative workers' outcomes, comprising turnover and social behaviors, work performance, tardiness, and nonattendance (Meyer et al., 2012; Saravanan & Udhayashankar, 2012).

In conjunction, several related studies have revealed the relationship of the variables such as organizational climate, transformational leadership and ethical leadership. Studies revealed that organizational climate and organizational commitment are significantly related. Dimensions of organizational climate had greater influence on organizational commitment. It was identified that positive climate can contribute to strong employee commitment. Specifically, organizational climate variables such as motivation, decision making, communication, leadership and goal setting are significant predictors of organizational commitment (Abdullah & Hasan, 2016; Bahrami, Taheri, Montazer Alalfaraj & Dehghani Tafti, 2013; Iqbal, 2008; Laschinger, Finegan & Shamian, 2011; Lok, Westwood & Crawford, 2015; McMurray, Scott & Pace, 2014; Warsi, Fatima & Sahibzada, 2009).

Similarly, leadership styles such as transformational and ethical leadership can also influence organizational commitment. There is considerable research now available suggesting that transformational leadership is positively associated with organizational commitment in a variety of organizational settings and cultures. Transformational leaders can influence followers' organizational commitment by promoting higher levels of intrinsic value associated with goal accomplishment, emphasizing the linkages between follower effort and goal achievement, and by creating a higher level of personal commitment on the part of the leader and followers to a common vision, mission, and organizational goals. Moreover, transformational leaders influence followers' organizational commitment by encouraging followers to think critically using novel approaches, involving followers in decision-making processes, inspiring loyalty, while recognizing and appreciating the different needs of each follower to develop his or her personal potential (Avolio, Zhu, Koh & Bathia, 2014; Bass & Avolio, 2014; Bono & Judge, 2013; Walumbwa & Lawler, 2013; Yammarino, Spangler & Bass, 2013).

In parallel, ethical leadership is also associated with employee organizational commitment. Leaders are the key in determining the outcome of organizational goals and in setting the tone for employee commitment which may include promotion, appraisal and strategies. If leaders are perceived to be ruthless and inconsiderate at work with others, employees tend to be less committed at work. Employees want to be associated with ethical leaders who are honest, credible, respectful and fair. Organizations can achieve better employee commitment when employees can work for truly responsible and ethical leaders. Thus, failing to be an ethical leader can lead to decrease employee commitment and consequently, lead to poor level of employee productivity (Agha, Nwekpa & Eze, 2017; Brown & Mitchell, 2010; Collins, 2011; Crane & Matten, 2014; Fisher & Lovell, 2013; Upadhyay & Singh, 2010).

Furthermore, the foregoing presentation and discussion of various literatures have helped in bringing into focus the important variables of the study, organizational climate, transformational leadership, ethical leadership, and organizational commitment. These served as support to the results and findings of the study.

In this context, in Figure 1 is shown the exogenous variables of the study, organizational climate, transformational leadership and ethical leadership while the endogenous variable is organizational commitment. Below are shown the hypothesized models which could best fit the organizational commitment of teachers.

Consequently, the main thrust of this study was to determine the best fit model of organizational commitment of teachers as estimated by organizational climate, transformational and ethical leadership of school heads among public elementary schools in Region XI, Philippines. Moreover, this study aimed to describe the level of organizational climate in terms of trusting relationship, job and goal setting freedom and organizational power direction. It also aimed to ascertain the level of transformational leadership of school heads in terms of charisma, social, vision, transactional, delegation, and execution. Further, it aimed to determine the level of ethical leadership of school heads in terms of people orientation, fairness, power sharing, concern for sustainability, ethical guidance, role clarification and integrity.

Likewise, it determined the level of organizational commitment of teachers in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment.

Moreover, it determined the significance of the relationship between the organizational climate and organizational commitment of teachers, transformational leadership of school heads and organizational commitment of teachers, and ethical leadership of school heads and organizational commitment of teachers. Lastly, it determined the model which best fits the organizational commitment of teachers among public elementary schools.

In consonance with the above objectives, the null hypotheses, stating that there is no significant relationship between the organizational climate and organizational commitment of teachers, transformational leadership of school heads and organizational commitment of teachers, and ethical leadership of school heads and organizational commitment of teachers, were tested at the .05 level of significance. There is also no model that best fits the organizational commitment of teachers among public elementary schools.

Significantly, in the global context, various researchers have revealed the importance of studying organizational commitment at work. Various authors (Ahmad, Yunus, Norwani & Musa, 2012; Bernaldez & Gempes, 2016; Haftkhavani, Faghiharam & Araghieh, 2012;

Hamid, Nordin, Adnan & Sirun, 2013; Saki, 2009) pronounced that the organizational commitment of teachers is very important since it is essential for school effectiveness and indirectly affects the learning outcome of the students. Schools more than ever need strong and committed teachers to attain educational goals. Moreover, committed teachers have more capabilities to cope with the obstacles in teaching at the classroom setting. An effective schoolteacher is a committed one who is constantly updating his/her knowledge to serve the students more and better. Thus, teachers' organizational commitment is a variable that affects the quality of teaching.

Furthermore, the findings of this study may be beneficial to the Department of Education, school heads, teachers, pupils and even future researchers. The result of the study may give information to the Department of Education officials regarding the organizational climate, transformational leadership, ethical leadership and organizational commitment at school. This study may provide ideas for DepEd officials to develop and implement programs which include activities and seminars that improve the organizational climate, transformational leadership, ethical leadership, and organizational commitment. Subsequently, findings of this study may also help the teachers in such a way that they may be aware of their own commitment at work. The teachers may have ideas on how to improve their normative, continuance and affective commitment which play an important role in attaining self-efficacy and effective performance at work. In addition, by increasing teachers' organizational commitment, the pupils are benefitted in a way that they receive effective and better delivery of instruction since teachers will be more committed to be both professionally and pedagogically prepared. Further, the result of the study may be beneficial to the school heads since they may acquire ample information and ideas about their transformational leadership and ethical leadership. School heads may mobilize their efforts to reform the school organization in general, in part by raising teachers' consciousness beyond personal interests to be more in line with organizational goals and vision. Further, they may also improve effective leadership, consistency, reliability, openness, respect, and integrity. Likewise, this study would serve as springboard of the future researcher for further studies about the related variables and related studies.

Methodology

Presented in this section are the discussions on the research respondents, materials and instrument, and design and procedure.

The respondents of the study were the 400 teachers from among public elementary schools in Region XI, Philippines for the school year 2022-2023. Stratified random method was used in determining the respondents of the study. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. In stratified random sampling or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is also called proportional random sampling or quota random sampling (Hayes, 2020).

Moreover, the researchers considered the inclusion and exclusion criteria in the selection of the respondents of the study. The teacher respondents were the regular teachers among public elementary schools in Region XI whose plantilla numbers were in the Department of Education. Teachers were willing to submit themselves and were permitted by their school heads to undergo the survey were included. Those teachers who voluntarily agreed with the informed consent were included in the survey; hence, teachers who clearly confessed their denial were excluded from the study. This study excluded those teachers coming from the private schools. Further, the researcher considered teachers who decided to withdraw or back out during the actual administration of the survey questionnaires.

The modified survey questionnaire used in this study was made up of four parts which are anchored from an adapted questionnaire, organizational climate, transformational leadership, ethical leadership and organizational commitment. These questionnaires were modified and subjected for validation by experts. The first draft of the research instrument was submitted to the research adviser for comments, suggestions and recommendations to improve its presentation with the corrections to be included and integrated. The final copies were submitted to a panel of experts for refinement. The final revision was made by incorporating the corrections, comments and suggestions given by the expert validators before the gathering of data. The consolidated results from the experts obtained an average weighted mean of 4.50, which has a verbal description of excellent.

Further, before the administration of the research instrument, a pilot testing was done to selected teachers who were not the respondents of the study. The survey questionnaire for the pilot test was subjected to the reliability testing using Internal Consistency Method. This was the most appropriate method to use since the test contains dichotomously scored items which the examinee either passes or fails in an item. The computed reliability of the instrument was > 0.70 for organizational climate questionnaire, > 0.70 for transformational leadership questionnaire, > 0.70 for ethical leadership questionnaire, and > 0.70 for organizational commitment questionnaire using Cronbach Alpha.

The questionnaire for organizational climate was adapted from Shanker (2015) with the following indicators: trusting relationship, job and goal setting freedom, and organizational power direction.

The level of organizational climate got an overall mean of 4.13 or high, with a standard deviation of 0.625. This means that the organizational climate among public elementary schools, as perceived by the teachers was oftentimes manifested.

Further, the questionnaire for transformational leadership was adapted from Clark (2011) with the following indicators: charisma, social, vision, transactional, delegation, and execution.

Computations yielded a grand mean of 4.36 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.643, indicating that the ethical leadership of

school heads is always manifested.

Further, the questionnaire for ethical leadership was adapted from Kalshoven (2010) which has the following indicators: people orientation, fairness, power sharing, concern for sustainability, ethical guidance, role clarification, and integrity.

Computations yielded a grand mean of 4.23 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.643, indicating that the organizational commitment of teachers among public elementary schools is always manifested.

Moreover, the questionnaire for the organizational commitment was adapted from Jaros (2007) with the following indicators: affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment.

Computations yielded a grand mean of 4.36 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.641, indicating that the organizational commitment of teachers among public elementary schools is always manifested.

Moreover, the quantitative, non-experimental design of research using correlational technique was used in this study. Correlational technique is a non-experimental design where researcher studies the correlation between variables in a normal setting without manipulation or control. In correlational studies, the researchers examine the strength of relationships among variables by looking into how change in one variable is linked with change in the other variable.

Generally, correlational method has independent and dependent variables, but the effect of independent variable is seen on dependent variable without manipulating the independent variable (Creswell, 2002).

Likewise, this study used Structural Equation Modeling. According to Lomax and Li (2013), this method combines factor analysis with path analysis to test theoretical relations among latent variables. Here models can range from simple to complex in nature in that any number of variables of any type can be involved (i.e., observed, latent, independent and/or dependent variables). The incorporation of factor analysis in structural equation modeling allows the researcher to use multiple measures of each latent variable instead of a single measure, thereby enabling better measurement conditions (i.e., reliability and validity) than with a single measure.

Structural equation modeling (SEM) is a powerful, multivariate technique found increasingly in scientific investigations to test and evaluate multivariate causal relationships. Further, SEM includes the statistical method of path analysis. Path analysis, on the other hand, had its beginning in biometrics and aimed to find the causal relationship among variables by creating a path diagram (Wright, 1921). The path analysis in earlier econometrics was presented with simultaneous equations (Haavelmo, 1943).

The structural model of Christensen, Johnson and Turner (2011) was used to test the hypothesized models and determine the best fit model for the organizational commitment of teachers.

This method was used to measure the relationship between and among organizational climate, transformational leadership, ethical leadership and organizational commitment of teachers among public elementary schools in Region XI, Philippines.

In the collection of data, the researcher asked permission from the Regional Director of DepEd-Region XI, then from the different Schools Division Superintendents. Upon their approval, the researcher then asked permission to the District Supervisors of each chosen District, and to the School Heads concerned, to allow the researcher to conduct the study to the 400 teachers. Upon approval, the researcher personally distributed and administered the research instruments to ensure their 100 percent retrieval.

During the administration of the survey questionnaire, the researcher made sure that no classes were interrupted. During the administration of questionnaires, the possible questions and clarifications of the respondents were personally addressed to the researcher. After the respondents had completely answered the necessary data needed in the questionnaire, the researcher retrieved all the questionnaires from the respondents. Then, a Certificate of Appearance was secured from the School Head concerned to vouch that the researcher honestly collected the data from the research respondents of the study. After the successful retrieval of the questionnaires, the data were collated and tabulated. Then, appropriate statistical tools were employed to derive the necessary data for interpretation and further analysis.

The following statistical tools were used in interpreting the data collated. Mean was used to describe the level of organizational climate, transformational leadership of school heads, ethical leadership of school heads, and organizational commitment of teachers in answer to sub-problems 1 to 4. Pearson r was used to determine the significance of the relationship between the organizational commitment of teachers and the exogenous variables (organizational climate, transformational leadership of school heads, and ethical leadership of school heads) in answer to sub-problem 5. Lastly., Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was used to test the hypothesized models and determine the best fit model for the organizational commitment of teachers among public elementary schools.

In the conduct of this study especially before the data were gathered, ethical issues and considerations were dealt. The researcher had undergone evaluation conducted by the members of ethics review committee. After several review process, this study was marked as passed and approved by the UM Ethics Review Committee (UMERC).

In terms of voluntary participation, the researcher ensured that the participation of the respondents was completely voluntary and anonymous to protect their privacy and no information was given whenever the respondents will not understand, before deciding whether to participate or not in the study.

To ensure privacy and confidentiality, the records of this study were kept confidential as far as permitted by law. Any identifiable information which was obtained in connection with this study remained confidential, except if necessary to protect the respondents' rights or welfare. The researcher did not allow the release of information about their participation to people who were not connected with the study. When the results of the study would be published or discussed in conference, no identifiable information would be used. Thus, this research adhered to the Data Privacy Act of 2012 which protected the teachers from unauthorized processing of their private or identifiable information and guaranteed them that their response cannot be traced back to its real sources to protect their identity.

Further, the respondents' name did not appear anywhere and no one except the researcher knew about respondents' specific answers. In line with the purpose of protecting the rights of the respondents all the information gather from this study were kept private and confidential.

Also, informed consent was secured from all the respondents involved in the study. The researcher conducted a detailed and comprehensive explanation regarding the purpose of the study to the respondents. The researcher ensured that the condition of the consent was a voluntary choice. The respondents had the sufficient information and adequate understanding of both the proposed research and the implications of their participation in the study, that the results may be utilized by the administrators for whatever purpose this may serve them best. The most important thing considered was that the form must bear the signature of the respondent which implies that he/she participated in the study voluntarily. Moreover, the respondents' personal and private information that were required in the study were treated with utmost care and were kept strictly confidential in accordance with the RA 10173 or Data Privacy Act of 2012 which ensured that all personal data shared were safeguarded and protected.

In terms of recruitment, the researcher ensured the appropriateness of identified recruiting parties and conducted a review of level of risks and measures to mitigate these risks (including physical, psychological, and social economic). The possible discomforts which could be encountered by the respondents during the survey were managed by the recruiting parties especially the researcher. The researcher was assisted by the school heads and teachers in meeting the number of respondents in the study.

As to risks, benefits, and safety, this research did not involve high risk situation that the population may experience on physical, psychological, or socioeconomic concerns. It protected and secured the rights of the individuals in the study. Likewise, with the result of this study, the researcher yielded generalizable knowledge about the condition of school employees especially the school heads and teachers. The results of this study can help the school heads and teachers since the findings of this study will give them new information about their work and their selves. Further, in the conduct of this research, the teacher respondents received tangible benefits such as a simple token from the researcher.

Moreover, the safety of the respondents was ensured using pseudonyms throughout the conduct of the research to protect their identities. Also, the data which were gathered from the survey were kept confidential and were utilized to verify findings of the study. Further, the researcher ensured health protocols amid COVID-19 pandemic during the seeking of organization's permission and approval as well as during the administration of survey questionnaires. To ensure health safety of everyone involved in the study, the researcher strictly adhered to the COVID-19 protocol from the IATF and local ordinances.

In terms of the avoidance of plagiarism, the researcher had undergone the turn-it-in software to ensure that no trace/evidence of misrepresentation of someone else's work as his own. The researcher made sure that the correct and accurate way of citing ideas from other writers and scholars was fully observed. To do this, this paper had undergone grammar checking via Grammarly software. As this study was based on several existing studies, the researcher made sure that he did not make any tale from his literature. Thus, all the information presented were carefully written and cited. All sources used in this study came from reliable journals and other scholarly works. This research complied with the citation rules of the APA 7th edition citation format hence there was no misrepresentation of work or alterations of any data gathered in the study. The data and information obtained were presented in the most accurate way of writing. Hence, there was no making up of data and/or results, or purposefully putting forward conclusions that were not accurate. No inconsistency with the existing literature among the information was found in manuscript. In the same manner, falsification was also taken into consideration in which no trace of purposefully misrepresenting the work to fit a model or theoretical expectation, no evidence of over claiming or exaggerations.

Additionally, since the researcher is a public-school teacher from the intended research locale there is a conflict of interest (COI). Thus, the researcher ensured to clearly eliminate the COI such as not conducting the survey among his peers and colleagues. Further, there was no set of conditions in which a professional judgment concerning primary interest such as the respondents' welfare or the validity of the research tends to be influenced by a secondary interest such as financial or academic gains or recognitions. The writings in this paper did not utilize any form of untruthfulness to harm the welfare of the respondents. All the information written were checked and validated by the panel of experts. Moreover, deceit was also avoided in which evidence that the benefit of misleading the respondents outweigh any potential harm to them.

In addition, the permission from the schools was ensured by the researcher. The researcher expressed getting a written permission from the organization in which the research had undertaken or the location in which the data were collected. When getting written permission, the researcher talked to the School Division Superintendent and concerned School Heads to give the permission sought and that the activities were organized well in advance. Also, the survey questionnaires utilized in this study were clear and

comprehensible; the researcher made sure that the respondents were fully aware of the benefits the school may get from the study through an informed consent. Thus, the survey was conducted with the approval of the concerned school authorities as well as the permission of the respondents themselves.

Lastly, this study considered authorship qualifications. The researcher, together with the help and guidance of the research adviser, substantially contributed to the conception and design, or acquisition of data, or analysis and interpretation of data. The researcher and adviser collaboratively drafted the article and revise it critically for important intellectual content. Both contributed to the study leading to the publication of the research.

Results and Discussion

Presented in this section are the data and analysis of findings based on the data obtained from the research instruments used in the study to determine the best-fit model of the organizational commitment of teachers among public elementary schools in Region XI, Philippines. Interpretations of results were engaged in the following subheadings: the level of organizational climate of teachers; the level of transformational leadership of school heads; the level of ethical leadership of school heads; the level of organizational commitment of teachers; the significance on the relationship between organizational climate and organizational commitment of teachers; the significance on the relationship between transformational leadership of school heads and organizational commitment of teachers; the significance on the relationship between ethical leadership of school heads and organizational commitment of teachers; and goodness of fit measures of the three structural equation models.

Level of Organizational Climate of Teachers

The first objective of this study was to determine the level of organizational climate of teachers. The level of organizational climate of teachers among public elementary schools is in terms of trusting relationship, job and goal setting freedom, and organizational power direction. The data on the organizational climate of teachers in public elementary schools is shown in Table 1. With a standard deviation of 0.625, the overall mean for the organizational climate of teachers was 4.13, which is high. This high level of organizational climate is due to the very high ratings of teachers in the domains trusting relationship, job and goal setting freedom, and organizational power direction. This indicates that organizational climate of teachers was oftentimes manifested. The data further implies that the existence of trusting relationships in school increases collaboration, while teachers are empowered by high job and goal-setting freedom. Positive attitudes toward organizational power direction imply effective leadership. Overall, the schools as an organization stresses a supportive and empowered environment for its teachers.

This aligns with the study of some authors (Pesania, 2022; Salip & Quines, 2023) which revealed the same result that level of organizational climate in the public schools was high. Likewise, it confirms the study of Montejo and Patino (2021) stating that teachers in select public elementary schools in Cebu City had a high regard for their schools' climate. Moreover, this finding of the study substantiates the ideas of several researchers (Ghavifekr & Pillai, 2016; Groza & Luchian-Ursachi, 2021; Valdez et al., 2019) which highlighted that the teachers have a more favorable school organizational climate.

Table 1. *Level of Organizational Climate of Teachers*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>D.E.</i>
Trusting Relationship	0.688	4.46	Very High
Job and Goal Setting Freedom	0.714	4.23	Very High
Organizational Power Direction	1.039	3.71	Very High
Overall	0.625	4.13	Very High

From this result, among the three indicators of organizational climate of teachers, trusting relationship attained the highest mean score of 4.46 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.688 while organizational power direction, the lowest, albeit high gained a mean score of 3.71 with a standard deviation of 1.039 which implies varied responses. This emphasizes a high level of trust within the organizational climate, notably between the school heads and the teachers and staff. This trust can be shown in the school head's respectful and approachable demeanor, their belief in the truthfulness of their statements and their willingness to pay attention to and address teachers' concerns. Overall, it indicates a healthy and harmonious working environment that values open communication and mutual trust. This aligns with various studies (Amzat, 2020; Arar, 2019; Balyer, 2017; Weinstein et al., 2020) stating that trusting relationship is built between principals and teachers in schools. Principals and teachers have different approaches to trust-building, with principals conferring trust and teachers earning it. In fact, these studies highlighted the importance of trust for school success and identified factors that assist or hinder trust. Trust, therefore, should be built to create enduring relationships among school community members. In addition, this expanded the idea presented in the study of Salip and Quines (2023) which avowed that it is important for school leaders to facilitate trust and mutual respect among teachers in schools.

The high level of organizational power direction as a domain of organizational climate suggests the school's significant need for autonomy and control. This is seen in its desire to be independent even when assistance is required, and in its will to maintain control in shared tasks. Furthermore, upper management is delegated significant power, stressing a top-down leadership model that promotes centralized decision-making and authority. This expands the idea of some authors (Shanker, 2015; Sudjarwo, 2019) that organizational power direction signifies direction of power in channelizing organizational energies. Power is assigned to its upper management and

sets higher standards of performance.

Level of Transformational Leadership of School Heads

The second objective was to determine the level of transformational leadership of school heads, which was measured through a survey questionnaire with the following indicators: charisma, social, vision, transactional, delegation, and execution. Shown in Table 2 are the data on the level of transformational leadership of school heads. Computations yielded a grand mean of 4.32 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.700, indicating that the level of transformational leadership of school heads is always manifested. This indicates that school leaders thrive at transformational leadership in terms of inspiring influence, excellent interpersonal skills, and a compelling vision for their schools. They effectively manage day-to-day skills. Their ability to execute plans and duties with skill constantly motivates and empowers their teachers, producing exceptional results in their schools. This is in line with the study of several authors (Maligsay & Quines, 2023; Quines & Pablo, 2023) which exposed the transformational leadership of school heads as very high in terms of charisma, social, vision, transactional, delegation, and execution. Also, this study substantiates the findings of the study of some researchers (Alhuzaim et al., 2022; Shrestha, 2020) which revealed that transformational leadership was the prevailing style of school leaders among schools. Transformational leadership in schools incorporates the charismatic and affective portions of leadership. High levels of transformational leadership are crucial for school transformation and improvement. Data reveals that the domain of transformational leadership of school heads that yielded the highest mean score was the social domain with a mean rating of 4.38 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.781.

Table 2. *Level of Transformational Leadership of School Heads*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>D.E.</i>
Charisma	0.799	4.33	Very High
Social	0.781	4.38	Very High
Vision	0.821	4.31	Very High
Transactional	0.787	4.32	Very High
Delegation	0.782	4.37	Very High
Execution	0.767	4.37	Very High
Overall	0.700	4.32	Very High

On the other hand, the lowest indicator, albeit very high is delegation which got a mean score of 4.23 with a standard deviation of 0.782. The very high level of transformational leadership of school heads in terms of social domain indicates that they actively promote teachers' and students' self-development by posing challenges that foster growth. They practice coaching and mentoring. Their empathetic presence at times of need demonstrates their dedication to fostering a nurturing and supportive educational environment. This supports the idea of Quines and Pablo (2023), that school heads practice social transformational leadership which means they have the inclination to help the teachers in learning by coaching and mentoring them. Further, it expanded the proposition of Sayyadi and Provitera (2022) which explained that as transformational leaders, leaders invest time in coaching others and recognize that each person has different needs, skills, and objectives. They also offer a variety of formal training programs to enhance job performance and assist organizational members in identifying and enhancing their strengths.

On the other hand, the very high of delegation leadership practices of school heads indicates that school leaders have an excellent capacity to delegation strategies for leadership, exhibiting a high level of confidence in teachers and students to pursue their educational objectives on their own. They avoid giving excessive guidance, believe in people's skills to attain their goals, and prioritize a smooth-running educational the environment. This type of leadership encourages autonomy, self-reliance, and responsibility in their educational community. This is in parallel with the studies of some authors (Doyle, 2020; Landry, 2020; Quines & Pablo, 2023) that the delegation with its high level suggests that the school heads can highly determine the division of tasks and distinguish the right person to accomplish such tasks. The delegation happens when the school leaders give their team members specific tasks to complete. School leaders can focus on tasks with a higher return on investment when they assign duties to teachers as team members; keeping them motivated and empowered. Likewise, it affirms the studies of Akinfolarin (2017), Dung & Hai (2020) Nkiruka et al., (2021), suggesting the importance of delegation of leaders as it reflects their willingness to delegate authority to subordinates so they can perform specific tasks and have access to the necessary resources. Delegation is a crucial component of the leadership method practiced by leaders.

Level of Ethical Leadership of School Heads

The third objective was to determine the level of ethical leadership of school heads which was measured through a survey questionnaire with the following indicators: people reaction, fairness, power sharing, concern for sustainability, ethical guidance, role clarification, and integrity. Shown in Table 3 are the data on the level of ethical leadership of school heads. Computations yielded a grand mean of 4.23 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.643, indicating that the level of ethical leadership of school heads is always manifested. This implies that school principals exhibit excellent ethical leadership by constantly following strong ethical principles such as integrity and fairness. Their dedication to ethical principles produces a morally grounded educational environment and builds trust and respect among teachers, students, and the greater school community. This ethical leadership style contributes to the establishment of an ethical and values-based culture. This is in line with the studies of several authors (Alemu, 2020; Topaloğlu, 2023; Vikaraman et al., 2020) stating that school principals have ethical leadership practice. School leaders in public schools are ethical in their administration in

which their teachers perceive them having moral values and principles.

Additionally, this finding substantiates the results of the studies of some authors (Davidson & Hughes, 2020; Ghanem, 2018; Waheed et al., 2019) which highlights that ethical leadership is crucial for the success of educational institutions, with leaders demonstrating values such as integrity, fairness, equity, and respect for diversity. Ethical leadership practices in schools include important concepts such as friendly and trusting relationships and ethically appropriate conduct. Hence, ethical leadership in schools is important in emphasizing the need for leaders to demonstrate ethical values.

Data reveals that the domain of ethical leadership of school heads that yielded the highest mean score was ethical guidance with a mean rating of 4.47 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.691.

On the other hand, the lowest indicator, albeit high was fairness which got a mean score of 3.47 with a standard deviation of 1.320.

Table 3. Level of Ethical Leadership of School Heads

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>D.E.</i>
People Orientation	0.825	4.24	High
Fairness	1.320	3.47	Very High
Power Sharing	0.733	4.26	Very High
Concern for Sustainability	0.743	4.42	Very High
Ethical Guidance	0.691	4.47	Very High
Role Clarification	0.722	4.38	Very High
Integrity	0.783	4.35	Very High
Overall	0.643	4.23	Very High

The very high level of ethical guidance indicates that school heads display a high level of ethical leadership by clearly defining integrity-related standards of conduct and behavior expected of teacher personnel. They constantly track compliance with integrity standards and recognize and reward ethical behavior. Furthermore, they emphasize the potential consequences of unethical behavior and encourage teacher discussions about integrity issues, building a culture of ethical awareness and responsibility within the school community. This confirms the ideas of some authors (Kalshoven et al., 2011; Mseti et al., 2023; Phuc et al., 2021) suggesting an ethical leader conveys standards regarding ethical conduct. They set rules, standards, and codes of conduct, which provide guidelines for ethical behavior. They also use rewards and punishments to hold subordinates responsible for their actions.

Moreover, the high level of fairness implies that school heads display a high level of fairness in their leadership by not holding individuals accountable for situations over which they have no influence or that are unrelated to their responsibilities. They also avoid seeking personal accomplishment at the expense of others and maintain a balanced focus on both personal and collective goals. This fair practice helps to create a fair educational atmosphere in which individual contributions are recognized and duties are shared fairly. This aligns with various studies (Goffnett, 2018; Mariama-Arthur & Mariama-Arthur, 2018; Ross et al., 2017; Trifu, 2019) which highlighted the importance of fairness in leadership. Leaders who promote fairness earn trust and fair leadership is crucial for the functionality and success of an organization. Also, it supports some studies (Kalshoven et al., 2011; Mseti et al., 2023; Phuc et al., 2021) which stated that fairness is seen as an important form of ethical leader behavior. Ethical leaders act with integrity and treat others fairly. They make principle and fair choices, are trustworthy and honest, do not practice favoritism, and take responsibility for their own actions.

Level of Organizational Commitment of Teachers

The fourth objective was to determine level of organizational commitment of teachers with the following indicators: affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment. Shown in Table 4 are the data on the level of organizational commitment of teachers. Computations yielded a grand mean of 4.36 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.641, and this indicates that the organizational commitment of teachers is always manifested. This implies that teachers' organizational commitment is marked by strong emotional attachment, a sense of moral obligation and an awareness of the consequences associated with leaving their existing professions. This multifaceted commitment reflects their true dedication to their schools and duties, which is motivated by both passion and a strong feeling of obligation, resulting in a strong commitment to the educational mission. This is line with the findings of several studies (Gökyer, 2018; Novikova et al., 2018) emphasizing the importance of organizational commitment of teachers. It was found out that teachers felt a strong commitment to the teaching profession. Also, it supports the study of Guhao (2019) which found that public school teachers in the Philippines exhibited high levels of organizational commitment.

From this result, the indicator of organizational commitment that yielded the highest mean was affective commitment with a mean score of 4.45 or very high, while the lowest indicator, albeit high was continuance commitment which gained a mean score of 4.19. The very high level of affective commitment of teachers suggests that teachers with a very high level of affective commitment demonstrate a strong emotional attachment and dedication to their work and their organization, demonstrating a deep and devoted commitment to their profession and the schools they serve. This is in parallel with findings of some authors (Burmansah et al., 2019; Santiago, 2019; Suryatika & Widyastuti, 2023) which revealed in their studies that teachers generally possess affective commitment. Teachers with high affective commitment can feel a strong emotional bond, loyalty and dedication to the school. Also, high affective

commitment leads to attachment to duties and obligations as a teacher.

Table 4. *Level of Organizational Commitment of Teachers*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>D.E.</i>
Affective Commitment	0.711	4.45	Very High
Continuance Commitment	0.810	4.19	Very High
Normative Commitment	0.671	4.44	Very High
Overall	0.641	4.36	Very High

Further, the high level of continuance commitment implies that teachers' commitment to their school organization stems from a perception of limited alternative options, a belief that staying is realistically important, and concern about the significant personal sacrifices and life disruptions that leaving would entail. This is in line with the avowal of some authors (Caballero & Guhao, 2020; Quines & Saycon, 2023) stating that employees demonstrate continuous commitment when they remain in an organization because of perceived financial and non-economic benefits. Employees are more likely to stay when they feel appreciated and perceive that leaving might endanger their future career possibilities due to uncertainty. Others may stay because they lack better career opportunities and are afraid of the consequences of quitting.

Significance on the Relationship between Organizational Climate and Organizational Commitment of Teachers

One important purpose of this study was to determine whether organizational climate has a significant relationship with the organizational commitment of teachers. As shown in table 5, the overall r-value on the correlation between the level of organizational climate and the level of organizational commitment was 0.543 with $p < 0.05$, which means that organizational climate is significantly associated with teachers' organizational commitment; hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Further, when the domains of organizational climate such as trusting relationship, job and goal setting freedom and organizational power direction were correlated to the overall organizational commitment of teachers, results of the computation yielded the r-values 0.564, 0.474 and 0.281 with all p-values less than 0.05, respectively, which can be all interpreted as significant. These factors are significantly related to the domains of teachers' organizational climate such as affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment.

Table 5. *Significance on the Relationship between Organizational Climate and Organizational Commitment of Teachers*

<i>Organizational Climate</i>	<i>Organizational Commitment</i>			
	<i>Affective Commitment</i>	<i>Continuance Commitment</i>	<i>Normative Commitment</i>	<i>Overall</i>
Trusting relationship	.592* (0.000)	.429* (0.000)	.473* (0.000)	.564* (0.000)
Job and Goal Setting Freedom	.449* (0.000)	.395* (0.000)	.406* (0.000)	.474* (0.000)
Organizational Power Direction	.147* (0.003)	.294* (0.000)	.293* (0.000)	.281* (0.000)
Overall	.470* (0.000)	.471* (0.000)	.491* (0.000)	.543* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level

Data implies the link between organizational climate, which includes aspects such as trust, job autonomy, and the direction of organizational authority, and teachers' organizational commitment emphasizes the school's environment's significant impact on teacher commitment. Trusting relationships, job autonomy, and organizational power alignment with teachers' goals all contribute to a positive organizational environment that supports teacher commitment. In essence, a supportive and empowering organizational climate in school greatly increases teachers' commitment to their educational institution. This aligns with the findings of several studies (Khan, 2019; Munte et al., 2022) which found a significant relationship between organizational work climate and teachers' organizational commitment in schools.

In addition, it confirms the findings of some previous studies (Abdullah & Hasan, 2016; Bahrami et al., 2013; Iqbal, 2008; Laschinger et al., 2011; Lok et al., 2015; McMurray et al., 2014; Warsi et al., 2009) which revealed that organizational climate and organizational commitment are significantly related. Dimensions of organizational climate had greater influence on organizational commitment. It was identified that positive climate can contribute to strong employee commitment.

Significance on the Relationship between Transformational Leadership and Organizational Commitment of Teachers

Another purpose of this study was to determine whether transformational leadership of school heads has a significant relationship with the organizational commitment of teachers. As shown in table 6, the overall r-values on the correlation between the level of transformational leadership of school heads and the level of organizational commitment of teachers was 0.627 with $p < 0.05$, which means that the transformational leadership of school heads is significantly associated with teachers' organizational commitment. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Moreover, when the domains of transformational leadership such as charisma, social, vision, transactional, delegation and execution

were correlated to the overall teachers; organizational commitment, results of the computation yielded the r-values of 0.552, 0.549, 0.543, 0.567, .540 and 0.590 with p-values of less than 0.05, respectively, which can be all interpreted as significant. These factors are significantly related to the domains of teachers’ organizational climate such as affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment.

The significant association between school leaders' transformational leadership and teachers' organizational commitment emphasizes the critical role of leadership in fostering teacher commitment. Transformational leaders show leadership practices in terms of charisma, social, vision, transactional, delegation, and execution.

Table 6. Significance on the Relationship between Transformational Leadership and Organizational Commitment of Teachers

Transformational Leadership	Organizational Commitment			Overall
	Affective Commitment	Continuance Commitment	Normative Commitment	
Charisma	.559* (0.000)	.428* (0.000)	.472* (0.000)	.552* (0.000)
Social	.581* (0.000)	.412* (0.000)	.461* (0.000)	.549* (0.000)
Vision	.549* (0.000)	.412* (0.000)	.478* (0.000)	.543* (0.000)
Transactional	.558* (0.000)	.456* (0.000)	.483* (0.000)	.567* (0.000)
Delegation	.508* (0.000)	.446* (0.000)	.471* (0.000)	.540* (0.000)
Execution	.620* (0.000)	.444* (0.000)	.499* (0.000)	.590* (0.000)
Overall	.633* (0.000)	.488* (0.000)	.538* (0.000)	.627* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level

This link underlines the importance of effective transformational leadership practices in educational settings, as it promotes teachers' commitment to their schools and shared goals. This confirms the proposition of some authors (Algothani & Mydin, 2022; Metaferia et al., 2023; Özkaya & Akin, 2023; Zacharo et al., 2018) which stated that teachers perceived a positive association and strong connection between transformational leadership and teachers’ organizational commitment to school goals particularly among public schools.

Significance on the Relationship between Ethical Leadership and Organizational Commitment of Teachers

This study also aimed to determine whether ethical leadership of school heads has a significant relationship with the organizational commitment of teachers.

Table 7. Significance on the Relationship between Ethical Leadership and Organizational Commitment of Teachers

Ethical Leadership	Organizational Commitment			Overall
	Affective Commitment	Continuance Commitment	Normative Commitment	
People Orientation	.620* (0.000)	.501* (0.000)	.435* (0.000)	.593* (0.000)
Fairness	.139* (0.005)	.245* (0.000)	.189* (0.000)	.221* (0.000)
Power Sharing	.644* (0.000)	.581* (0.000)	.550* (0.000)	.675* (0.000)
Concern for Sustainability	.662* (0.000)	.546* (0.000)	.570* (0.000)	.674* (0.000)
Ethical Guidance	.649* (0.000)	.480* (0.000)	.520* (0.000)	.624* (0.000)
Role Clarification	.607* (0.000)	.492* (0.000)	.529* (0.000)	.616* (0.000)
Integrity	.617* (0.000)	.456* (0.000)	.508* (0.000)	.598* (0.000)
Overall	.673* (0.000)	.581* (0.000)	.572* (0.000)	.693* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level

As shown in Table 7, the overall r-values on the correlation between the level of ethical leadership of school heads and the level of organizational commitment of teachers was 0.693 with $p < 0.05$, which means that the ethical leadership of school heads is significantly associated with teachers’ organizational commitment. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies a significant connection between school leaders' ethical leadership and teachers' organizational commitment. Ethical leadership entails decision-making values such as fairness and integrity. When school leaders demonstrate ethical leadership, they create an environment in which teachers feel

respected and valued, leading to increased commitment to the school.

Further, when the domains of ethical leadership such as people reaction, fairness, power sharing, concern for sustainability, ethical guidance, role clarification and integrity were correlated to the overall teachers’ organizational commitment, results of the computation yielded r-values ranging from 0.593 to 0.598 with the p-values of less than 0.05, respectively, which can be all interpreted as significant. These factors are significantly related to the teachers’ organizational climate such as affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment.

This confirms the statements of some authors (Agha et al., 2017; Brown & Mitchell, 2010; Collins, 2011; Crane & Matten, 2014; Fisher & Lovell, 2013; Upadhyay & Singh, 2010) that ethical leadership is associated with employee organizational commitment. Leaders set the tone for employee commitment which may include promotion, appraisal and strategies. If leaders are perceived to be considerate at work with others, employees tend to be more committed at work. Employees want to be associated with ethical leaders that are honest, credible, respectful and fair. Organizations can achieve better employee commitment when employees can work for truly responsible and ethical leaders. Thus, an ethical leader can increase employee commitment.

Best Fit Model on Organizational Commitment of Teachers

The original proposed model outlined in Figure 1 requires some modification to fit the data. There were three generated models presented in the study. In identifying the best fit model, all indices included must consistently fall within the acceptable ranges. Chi-square/ degrees of freedom value should be less than 2 but greater than 0 with its corresponding p-value greater than 0.05. Root Mean Square Error Approximation value must be less than 0.05 and its corresponding P-close value must be greater than 0.05. The other indices such as the normed fit index, Tucker-Lewis’s index, comparative fit index and the goodness of fit index must all be greater than 0.95.

Generated Model 1. In Figure 2 is shown the generated Structural Model 1. It displays the interrelationships of the exogenous variables: organizational climate with its three indicators: trusting relationship, job and goal setting freedom and organizational power direction; transformational leadership with its six indicators: charisma, social, vision, transactional, delegation and execution; ethical leadership with seven indicators: people reaction, fairness, power sharing, concern for sustainability, ethical guidance, role clarification and integrity and their causal relationship on the endogenous variable teachers’ organizational commitment as its indicators. All indices did not reach the acceptable ranges as shown in Table 8. Hence, a poor fit.

Generated Model 2. The generated Model 2 is shown in Figure 3. It exhibits the interrelationships of the exogenous variables where some indicators with low values were removed. It can be seen that three retained indicators—specifically, trusting relationship, job and goal setting freedom and organizational power direction—have demonstrated a positive influence within the organizational climate. Similarly, within the realm of transformational leadership, positive influence is evident in its remaining two indicators namely, transactional and execution.

Figure 2. Structural Equation Model 1 in Standardized Solution

Legend: tr, Trusting Relationship; jgsf, Job and Goal Setting Freedom; opd, Organizational Power Direction; OC, Organizational Climate; cha, Charisma; soc, Social; vis, Vision; tran, Transactional; del, Delegation; exe, Execution; TL, Transformational Leadership; po, People Orientation; fai, Fairness; ps, Power Sharing; cs, Concern for Sustainability; eg, Ethical Guidance; rc, Role Clarification; int, Integrity; EL, Ethical Leadership; ac, Affective Commitment; cc, Continuance Commitment; nc, Normative Commitment; OrgCom, Organizational Commitment

Table 8. Goodness of Fit Measures of Structural Equation Model 1

INDEX	CRITERION	MODEL FIT VALUE
P-Close	> 0.05	.000
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2	4.068
P-Value	> 0.05	.000
GFI	> 0.95	.847
CFI	> 0.95	.935
NFI	> 0.95	.916
TLI	> 0.95	.924
RMSEA	< 0.05	.088

Legend: CMIN/DF, Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom; NFI, Normed Fit Index; TLI, Tucker-Lewis Index; CFI, Comparative Fit Index; GFI, Goodness of Fit Index; RMSEA, Root Means Square of Error Approximation; P-close, P of Close Fit; P-value, Probability Level

Ethical leadership as indicated in the model, displays positive influence through its three retained indicators particularly, people orientation, role clarification and integrity. In contrast, teachers’ organizational commitment is positively influenced by its three retained indicators: affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment. It is noteworthy that all remaining indicators exert a direct influence on organizational commitment of teachers, emphasizing the comprehensive impact of the three exogenous variables on the endogenous variable.

Commitment. It is noteworthy that all remaining indicators exert a direct influence on organizational commitment of teachers, emphasizing the comprehensive impact of the three exogenous variables on the endogenous variable.

Figure 3. Structural Equation Model 2 in Standardized Solution

Legend: tr, Trusting Relationship; jgsf, Job and Goal Setting Freedom; opd, Organizational Power Direction; OC, Organizational Climate; cha, Charisma; soc, Social; vis, Vision; tran, Transactional; del, Delegation; exe, Execution; TL, Transformational Leadership; po, People Orientation; fai, Fairness; ps, Power Sharing; cs, Concern for Sustainability; eg, Ethical Guidance; rc, Role Clarification; int, Integrity; EL, Ethical Leadership; ac, Affective Commitment; cc, Continuance Commitment; nc, Normative Commitment; OrgCom, Organizational Commitment

Table 9. Goodness of Fit Measures of Structural Equation Model 2

INDEX	CRITERION	MODEL FIT VALUE
P-Close	> 0.05	.003
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2	3.238
P-Value	> 0.05	.000
GFI	> 0.95	.942
CFI	> 0.95	.975
NFI	> 0.95	.961
TLI	> 0.95	.960
RMSEA	< 0.05	.075

Legend: CMIN/DF, Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom; NFI, Normed Fit Index; TLI, Tucker-Lewis Index; CFI, Comparative Fit Index; GFI, Goodness of Fit Index; RMSEA, Root Means Square of Error Approximation; P-close, P of Close Fit; P-value, Probability Level

Furthermore, Model 2 exhibited significant improvements in various indices compared to Model 1. Notably, the CMIN/DF ratio improved from 4.068 to 3.238, although it still falls short of acceptability, as it does not meet the required criterion of $0 < \text{value} < 2$. The GFI also demonstrated an increase from .847 to .942, yet it remains below the necessary threshold of 0.95 for a satisfactory fit. Additionally, the RMSEA decreased from .088 to .075, but it remains unacceptable, failing to meet the required criterion of < 0.05 . The P-value maintained the same value of .000 in both models while the P-close increased from .000 to .003, indicating a poor fit as they do not satisfy the criterion of > 0.05 . Although the CFI improved from .935 to .975, the NFI increased from .916 to .961, and the TLI rose from .924 to .960—meeting acceptable criteria individually—it is essential to emphasize that achieving a good fit requires meeting all criteria collectively. Thus, despite improvements in certain indices, comprehensive adherence to all criteria is imperative for deeming the model a good fit. Hence, a poor fit.

Generated Model 3. Lastly, the generated Model 3 exhibited in figure 4 showed the interrelationships of the exogenous variables: organizational climate of teachers, transformational leadership and ethical leadership and their causal relationship on the endogenous variable teachers’ organizational commitment. Model 3 is a modified version of Models 1 and 2, wherein some indicators with low values were removed.

Furthermore, the substantial improvement among indices were manifested in Model 3 when compared to Model 2, such as P-Close of .003 to .689; CMIN/DF of 3.238 to 1.632; P-value of .000 to .063; GFI of .942 to .986; CFI of .972 to .996; NFI, of .916 to .961; TLI, of .924 to .992 and RMSEA of .075 to .040; all fall within the acceptable ranges.

Moreover, the structural modifications revealed that teachers’ organizational commitment was defined by its retained indicators: affective commitment and continuance commitment. On the other hand, organizational climate was described by its domains: trusting relationship and job and goal setting freedom; while transformational leadership was determined by its retained indicators: transactional and execution.

Figure 4. Structural Equation Model 3 in Standardized Solution

Legend: tr, Trusting Relationship; jgsf, Job and Goal Setting Freedom; opd, Organizational Power Direction; OC, Organizational Climate; cha, Charisma; soc, Social; vis, Vision; tran, Transactional; del, Delegation; exe, Execution; TL, Transformational Leadership; po, People Orientation; fai, Fairness; ps, Power Sharing; cs, Concern for Sustainability; eg, Ethical Guidance; rc, Role Clarification; int, Integrity; EL, Ethical Leadership; ac, Affective Commitment; cc, Continuance Commitment; nc, Normative Commitment; OrgCom, Organizational Commitment

Finally, ethical leadership was measured by its two retained domains people orientation and integrity. Model 3 was found to have indices that consistently direct a very good fit to the data because all the indices presented fall within each criterion as shown in Table 10. Thus, there was no need to find another model for testing because it was already found to be the best fit among all the tested models. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no best fit model was rejected.

It could be stated that there is a best fit model that predicts the organizational commitment of teachers in Region XI. The model clearly illustrates the importance of organizational climate, transformational leadership and ethical leadership as predictors of teachers’ organizational commitment. However, it could be gathered from the model that out of three indicators of organizational climate, only two remained as significant predictor of teachers’ organizational commitment to wit: trusting relationship and job and goal setting freedom. This aligns with various studies (Amzat, 2020; Arar, 2019; Balyer, 2017; Weinstein et al., 2020) stating that trusting relationship is built

between principals and teachers in schools. Principals and teachers have different approaches to trust-building, with principals conferring trust and teachers earning it. In fact, these studies highlighted the importance of trust for school success and identified factors that assist or hinder it. Trust, therefore, should be built to create enduring relationships among school community members. In addition, this expanded the idea presented in the study of Salip and Quines (2023) which avowed that it is important for school leaders to facilitate trust and mutual respect among teachers in schools.

Table 10. *Goodness of Fit Measures of Structural Equation Model 3*

INDEX	CRITERION	MODEL FIT VALUE
P-Close	> 0.05	.689
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2	1.632
P-Value	> 0.05	.063
GFI	> 0.95	.986
CFI	> 0.95	.990
NFI	> 0.95	.992
TLI	> 0.95	.998
RMSEA	< 0.05	.040

Legend: CMIN/DF, Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom; NFI, Normed Fit Index; TLI, Tucker-Lewis Index; CFI, Comparative Fit Index; GFI, Goodness of Fit Index; RMSEA, Root Means Square of Error Approximation; P-close, P of Close Fit; P-value, Probability Level

Further, this model explained organizational climate in terms of perception of people related to performance goals and opportunities for independent thoughts and action that can help them and the organization alike. It is also perceived by the subordinate that it gives full freedom to decide about completing their assigned job (Shanker, 2015).

Furthermore, the result of this study reinforced the findings that the teachers' organizational commitment predicted with transformational leadership (Algothani & Mydin, 2022; Metaferia et al., 2023; Özkaya & Akin, 2023; Zacharo et al., 2018). The proposition stated that teachers perceived a positive association and strong connection between transformational leadership and teachers' organizational commitment to school goals, particularly among public schools.

In addition, the impact that transformational leadership has on members of an organization can best be examined by comparing it to transactional leadership, where leaders approach followers with an eye to exchanging one thing for another. A transformational leader mobilizes their followers toward reform by an appeal to values and emotions. Transformational leadership focuses more on self-actualization - a desire for the betterment of the team or organization. Thus, transformational approaches to leadership have a wide range of potential benefits. At the organization level, transformational leadership practices can produce strategic organizational change. Perceived transformational actions have also been shown to increase staff satisfaction and reduce stress and burnout (Edwards, Knight, Broome & Flynn, 2010; Martin & Epitropaki, 2011; Judge & Piccolo, 2014; Seltzer, Numerof, & Bass, 2009; Waldman, Javidan, & Varella, 2014).

In transactional leadership, the leader ensures others understand what you expect from them by using mutual agreement. In addition, they ensure that if poor performance does occur, they take action to ensure it does not affect the moral of the team while in the execution, a leader does delegate as many tasks as possible with the authority to accomplish them, as a good steward of the department's resources, and do follow-up to ensure things are going as planned and time is not wasted (Clark, 2011).

Subsequently, only two of the seven indicators of ethical leadership, power orientation and integrity remain as predictors of teachers' organizational commitment. This confirms the statement of some authors (Agha et al., 2017; Brown & Mitchell, 2010; Collins, 2011; Crane & Matten, 2014; Fisher & Lovell, 2013; Upadhyay & Singh, 2010) that ethical leadership is associated with employee organizational commitment. Leaders set the tone for employee commitment which may include promotion, appraisal and strategies. If leaders are perceived to be considerate at work with others, employees tend to be more committed at work. Employees want to be associated with ethical leaders that are honest, credible, respectful and fair. Organizations can achieve better employee commitment when employees can work for truly responsible and ethical leaders. Thus, an ethical leader can increase employee commitment.

The people orientation component in ethical leadership reflects genuinely caring about, respecting and supporting subordinates and where possible ensuring that their needs are met (Kalshoven, Den Hartog & De Hoogh, 2011; Kanungo & Conger, 2013; Treviño et al., 2013).

Integrity behaviors, as based on the literature, are described as word-deed alignment or the extent to which what one says is in line with what one does (Ferdig, 2017; Kalshoven et al., 2011). Leaders who keep promises and behave consistently can be trusted or believed because they work or behave as expected. Similarly, leaders are being ethical when they keep promises and behave consistently. Thus, ethical leaders keep their promises and act consistently, in a predictable way, which we label integrity (Kalshoven, 2010; Yukl, 2016).

On the part of organizational commitment of teachers, only two out of three indicators remained to be measured, these were perceived affective commitment and continuance commitment. This substantiates the statement of Handford and Leithwood (2013), Ismail and Daud (2014) to achieve success in organizational commitment, every organization needs effective leadership. Studies found out that teachers trust school leaders if they possess effective leadership, consistency, reliability, openness, respect and integrity which constitutes ethical leadership. These practices are likely to encourage teachers to be more committed to their careers.

In parallel, the commitment of the people inside the organization directly impacts their job performance (Malhotra & Mukherjee, 2014; Steyrer, Schiffinger & Lang, 2014). To nurture high level of commitment of the organizational members, every leader should reassure participative decision-making, treat organizational members with respect, and show fairness and caring attitude towards them. As organizational leaders display ethical leadership, there will be an increased organizational commitment among employees (Cullen, Parboteeah & Victor, 2013; Ferreira, 2012; Walumbwa & Lawler, 2013).

Relatively, a three-component model of commitment was established by Meyer and Allen who perhaps governs research regarding organizational commitment (Jaros, 2007; Meyer, Stanley, Herscovitch & Topolnytsky, 2012; Meyer & Herscovitch, 2011). In particular, the first is affective commitment which is the emotional attachment of the people to the organization and a conviction in its values. This domain reveals commitment based on emotional connections the workers cultivate with the organization principally through helpful job experiences (Meyer et al., 2012; Saravanan & Udhayashankar, 2012).

Further, the second is the continuance commitment refers to the observed cost-effective value of staying with the organization compared to separating from it. This domain reveals commitment based on both social and economic cost of exiting the organization (Meyer et al., 2012; Saravanan & Udhayashankar, 2012).

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, conclusions were drawn as follows:

For the descriptive level of the exogenous variables, organizational climate is high while transformational leadership of school heads and ethical leadership of school heads are very high, which signifies that these variables are oftentimes to always manifested. Meanwhile, the endogenous variable—organizational commitment of teachers, with a very high descriptive level, signifies that the teachers' organizational commitment is always manifested.

The significant relationships between organizational climate and organizational commitment of teachers, and between transformational leadership of school heads and organizational commitment of teachers as well as between ethical leadership of school heads and organizational commitment of teachers imply that any increase in organizational climate, transformational leadership and ethical leadership of school heads results in a corresponding increase in the organizational commitment of teachers.

The structural model indicates the best fit model for the organizational commitment of teachers as proven by the summary of the goodness of fit satisfying all the indices for a structural equation model.

The significant direct effect of organizational climate, transformational leadership, and ethical leadership of school heads on the organizational commitment of teachers implies that teachers' organizational commitment is influenced by school heads' transformational leadership and ethical leadership along with organizational climate.

The study was anchored on the Social Exchange Theory of Homans (1958). According to this theory, people seek a fair exchange relationship with their organization. If employees perceive a low risk, the exchange relationship will be balanced, and their loyalty to the organization and their willingness to stay will increase. This can explain how organizational climate improves organizational commitment of employees.

Further, the study was also anchored on the Theory of Leader-member Ex-change (LMX) of Cerstner & Day (1997). This theory helps to explain the impact of LMX relationship on the attitudes and the behaviors of subordinates at work. According to Hui et al. (2004), the leader clearly conveys role expectations to his followers, then he provides them with both tangible and intangible rewards that meet expectations, fulfilled or not. This theory can best explain the determination of the relationship leadership styles and organizational commitment as one the objectives of this study.

Finally, findings showed that organizational climate and transformational and ethical leadership of school heads were significantly correlated with teachers' organizational commitment. Model 3 emerged as the best-fit structural model for teachers' organizational commitment as it indicated that by structural modifications, the organizational climate was described by trusting relationship as well as job and goal setting freedom while the two remaining indicators described the variable, transformational leadership: transactional and execution. Similarly, two retained indicators measured ethical leadership: people orientation and integrity. On the other hand, organizational commitment was defined by affective commitment and continuance commitment. This implies that schools may focus on implementing leadership training enhancement activities for all school heads in public elementary schools as part of their staff development program.

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are suggested.

The following indicators got the lowest means: organizational power direction for organizational climate; delegation for school heads' transformational leadership; fairness for school heads' ethical leadership, and continuance commitment for teachers' organizational commitment. Hence, the Department of Education may empower middle management and foster a culture of shared decision-making involving teachers and staff. School heads may encourage teacher autonomy in their classrooms while regularly evaluating decision-making processes can also help strike a better balance. Additionally, promoting leadership development among teachers and staff can

enhance shared leadership and contribute to more effective organizational power direction. Further, school heads may undergo specialized leadership development programs that emphasize effective delegation skills. Likewise, the DepEd may prioritize leadership training programs that emphasize fairness and ethical conduct among school heads. Further, school heads may offer ongoing professional development to make teachers more competitive, foster a culture of recognition and appreciation, and create clear career advancement pathways to improve teacher continuance commitment.

Further, it was found that the best fitting model shows that the organizational climate, transformational leadership, and ethical leadership of school heads have significant direct effect on teachers' organizational commitment. Hence, it is recommended that the schools may prioritize the cultivation of a positive organizational climate characterized by trust and collaboration. Investing in leadership development programs for school heads to improve their transformational and ethical leadership skills is crucial, as effective leadership plays a significant role in fostering commitment. Promoting ethical leadership practices and transparent decision-making is essential to set a positive example for the entire school community. Facilitating open and continuous communication, implementing recognition and appreciation programs, and establishing feedback mechanisms for teachers are vital to build trust and enhance commitment. Encouraging collaborative decision-making processes that involve teachers in important organizational decisions can further increase their sense of ownership and commitment to the school's mission and goals, ultimately creating a more engaged and dedicated educational environment.

For future researchers, it is important to delve deeper into the factors influencing organizational commitment in education. They may explore moderating factors or may conduct comparative research across different educational levels to gain a comprehensive understanding. Additionally, researchers may consider the impact of technology on commitment, particularly in remote or hybrid teaching environments. Qualitative approaches, such as interviews and case studies, may provide valuable insights into teachers' subjective experiences and perceptions regarding commitment and leadership in their specific school contexts.

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